

Corporate Social Responsibility of selected FMCG companies in India during COVID 19 Pandemic – A Review Analysis.

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Abstract:

Corporate social responsibility (CSR) has historically been an option for businesses looking to boost their reputation in the community and demonstrate their commitment to good corporate citizenship. However, the COVID 19 pandemic has significantly affected the industry. Companies are now realising how dramatically and abruptly their connection with their stakeholders has changed. The financial burden on the government, companies, and people has increased due to the corona virus pandemic. In order to better understand the corporate social responsibility (CSR) activities carried out by various companies in India during the COVID 19 pandemic, this research paper has made a review and analysis of a comparative study on the CSR initiatives of some companies in India during the COVID 19 pandemic. To learn about the actions done by the businesses for the benefit of the country, society, and individuals as well, a number of business case studies have been analysed.

Keywords: Fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG), COVID 19 Pandemic, Contribution, Rural Development, Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) initiatives.

Introduction:

The idea behind corporate social responsibility (CSR) stems from the idea that because businesses interact with society and use its resources, they have a moral obligation to do so. An organisation fulfils its obligations to the environment, workers, communities, stakeholders, customers, and other societal members when it implements CSR principles.

The following justifications explain why CSR is becoming more significant:

i. Public Expectations from the Enterprise - This relates to what the general public expects of an enterprise, whether they are connected to it directly or indirectly. If the business satisfies the requirements, wants, and demands of society, it can operate peacefully. However, it would be challenging for an organisation to continue to operate if it did not meet societal expectations. Therefore, if a company wants to stay in business over the long term, it must cater to the requirements of society.

ii. Better Business Environment - This refers to creating a conducive environment for an enterprise's business activities. The atmosphere for the enterprise is beneficial if society is pleased with the company's business operations.

iii. A positive public image - aids a business in attracting more clients and better workers. Building and sustaining a positive public image, thus, aids in enhancing business performance.

iv. Power and Responsibility - This is a crucial issue that needs to be properly balanced. An organisation has social power because its actions affect the environment, customers, employees, and numerous other facets of society. Therefore, any

decision that is made inequitably could have a detrimental impact on society's well-being.

A company's responsibilities include:

The following are some examples of an enterprise's obligations:

i. Economic responsibility - Economic responsibility is the obligation of the business to provide goods and services to the community. To be able to pay employees' wages, make payments to creditors and other stakeholders, and generate regular profits, the business must set a fair and reasonable price for its products.

ii. Legal Responsibility - This concept relates to an organization's obligation to uphold the law. These obligations under the law are made by the government and automatically become regulations that businesses must abide by. For instance, the government establishes environmental rules to reduce noise, water, and air pollution and maintain the ecosystem. All factories must abide by these laws in order to maintain efficient business operations and prevent legal action.

iii. Ethical Responsibility - This concept refers to an organization's legal obligation to uphold society's moral and ethical norms. The people who make up the society anticipate that businesses would act to stop unethical behaviour and adhere to social norms.

iv. Discretionary Responsibility - This refers to the company's moral duty to the community. It includes the obligation of the business to contribute to the welfare of society, such as through educating the impoverished and educating unskilled workers. Discretionary authority is entirely a matter of choice.

The fourth-largest economic sector in India is the fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG) business. The sector has grown significantly as a result of rising

public knowledge, improved access to goods and services, and changing lifestyles. With more newlyweds choosing to rely on quick and simple domestic and culinary solutions, the business is expected to expand. Numerous industry participants have committed their CSR funds in India to address these challenges because the sector is skilled at offering solutions for concerns like nutrition and sanitation, among others.

Review of Literature

Pooja Yadav and Dr. Abhaya Ranjan Srivastava's (2021) paper from has provided The financial burden on the government, companies, and people has increased due to the corona virus pandemic. Therefore, the focus of this research article is to better comprehend the corporate social responsibility (CSR) initiatives taken by different commercial organisations in India during the COVID 19 pandemic. To learn about the actions done by the businesses for the benefit of the country, society, and individuals as well, a number of business case studies have been analysed. Prof. Pavankumar C. Ramgouda, Dr. Praveen B. Patil. (2021), He came to the conclusion in this article that both HUL and ITC Ltd. make significant contributions to society through their different CSR projects and programmes. They are primarily concentrating on rural development, health and hygiene, women's empowerment, and education. Bala Krishnamoorthy and Poojaa Gokarna (2021), Through exploratory research, this study offers insights into the CSR tactics used by Indian corporations during the COVID-19 pandemic. The study is based on semi-structured interviews with 27 CSR managers who help their firms strategize and carry out CSR initiatives. The findings highlight the dedication demonstrated by corporations to reducing the effects of the virus through a variety of CSR initiatives. As a result, this study contributes to our understanding of CSR and serves as a foundation for future studies on COVID-19 and CSR.

Objectives of the research:

1. To go over Corporate Social Responsibility's significance.
 2. To learn about certain FMCG companies' CSR efforts in India during the COVID 19 pandemic
- Research Methodology:

Purpose of the study: The purpose of the study was to comprehend the value of corporate social responsibility for commercial enterprises as well as the key areas in which the businesses focused their CSR efforts throughout the pandemic.

Data collection: For this article, we only used secondary data, which we obtained by looking through a variety of internet databases, journals, conference proceedings, research papers, annual reports of selected organisations, company websites, etc.

FMCG Companies' Spending on CSR Projects:

Let's examine the five FMCG firms in India that prioritise CSR in this environment.

Hindustan Unilever:

HUL is dedicated to managing and expanding its company in a socially conscious manner. Their goal is to expand their business while minimising the negative effects of their activities on the environment and enhancing the benefits to society. In the last five years, the corporation has spent more than 500 crores on its CSR initiatives, consistently exceeding the minimum required under CSR law. With the help of its CSR money, Hindustan Unilever Limited tackles problems affecting India's development. In the areas of water conservation and addressing health and hygiene problems at the community level, it has had great success. Through the Hindustan Unilever Foundation, the corporation carries out its CSR projects (HUF). The non-profit serves as a vehicle for Hindustan Unilever Limited's environmental and community development projects pertaining to water management. With an emphasis on empowering local community institutions to manage water resources and enhancing farm-based livelihoods through the adoption of wise water management techniques, HUF runs the "Water for Public Good" initiative. Since 2010, 23 NGOs and over 4,300 villages in India have partnered with HUF to promote grassroots interventions in 53 districts.

ITC Limited:

ITC has been concentrating its CSR efforts on India's rural development. In 2019–20, the corporation spent more on CSR efforts than in any prior year, at Rs. 326.49 crores. The company is actively involved in social programmes in the fields of sport, culture, sustainable agriculture, healthcare, and digital literacy. ITC Choupal is a long-running flagship CSR programme by the business that has elevated community development internationally to a gold standard. Through digital literacy and economic empowerment, ITC Choupal has not only helped thousands of farmers over the years, but it has also been copied by a large number of other corporations for social welfare in their own communities. ITC has led a CSR initiative to enable the creation of an eco-system that would lead to significant livelihood generation for farmers and daily wage earners under the ambit of the Government's MGNREG Scheme. This is in keeping with its commitment to put Nation First and in response to the needs arising out of the lockdown implemented to contain the first wave of COVID-19 pandemic.

During the second wave, the company supplied oxygen cryogenic canisters to oxygen concentrators and generators in an effort to lessen the situation. ITC partnered with Linde India to airfreight 24 cryogenic ISO containers, each weighing 20 tonnes,

from Asian nations in order to deliver medical oxygen across India. This served the national priority of alleviating the bottleneck associated with transporting medical oxygen. The CSR project follows a severe medical oxygen shortage that is limiting the ability of the healthcare sector to treat coronavirus patients.

A significant quantity of oxygen concentrators are also transported to ITC for distribution. The organization's paperboards unit in Bhadrachalam has started supplying nearby areas with oxygen.

Britannia:

Britannia CSR places the greatest emphasis on healthcare and nutrition in India. With its many undernutrition and malnutrition solutions, the company has a positive impact on the community. A significant part of Britannia's CSR strategy is nutrition research and development. The business established the Britannia Nutrition Foundation (BNF), which has been around for more than ten years, to carry out its CSR initiatives to address these concerns. Its main objective is to uphold every child's right to nutrition and growth. BNF operates lengthy, reproducible programmes in a number of states. Considering that BNF is in charge of ensuring the health and vitality of the entire community in which it operates, community development is regarded as a focus area.

The business supports reducing, recycling, and recovering plastic when it comes to use in production and the supply chain. The R&D team is looking for ways to use less plastic in the distribution system, manufacturing, and office spaces. Plastic trays were taken out of the product lineup as one stage. In keeping with the circular economy that reputable international companies are adopting, research and development is focused on developing 100% reusable packaging.

In times of need, Britannia CSR steps forward to help the populace. Without a doubt, the COVID-19 epidemic is the worst humanitarian catastrophe the world has ever experienced. The corporate social responsibility team at Britannia organised its personnel and assets to support individuals in need. The provision of vital meals was at the top of the list of actions taken in reaction to the pandemic because food is the company's primary line of business. In 19 states, the Wadia Group distributed 1.35 billion meals (and meal equivalents) and 90 lakh packs of biscuits and bakery goods. The team sent out personnel in the infrastructure of the supply chain and collaborated with organisations to deliver vital meals to the people whose lives had been upended by the coronavirus. Daily wage labourers, migrant families, and domestic helpers who had lost their jobs to low-income families and anganwadis were given nourishing food.

Marico:

The concept of social responsibility is seen at Marico Limited as a moral and ethical duty rather than as a requirement. Across the board, the company aspires to "Make a difference." Chairman Harsh Mariwala is deeply committed to philanthropy, social welfare, and combating climate change. In FY 2019–20, Marico spent Rs 19 crores on initiatives promoting community welfare. In order to establish and uplift the local communities in and around operations while fostering a harmonious relationship with them, the company has created community sustenance initiatives. Kalpavriksha, the company's major CSR initiative, aims to improve the well-being and output of coconut growers. As part of Kalpavriksha, several important activities are promoted, including improved crop productivity now, hybrid plantation, replantation, proper water management, and use of technological intervention. Under its aegis, Kalpavriksha has also begun a number of programmes in many fields, including training, a digital channel, and agricultural care workers. The corporation contributed Rs. 12 crores to the effort to contain the epidemic during the COVID crisis. In some places, the corporation gave sanitizers worth Rs. 1 crore to front-line workers like government agencies, the police, hospitals, and medical staff. The business committed to working with GiveIndia to raise Rs. 2 crore. The money will be used to enhance the healthcare system in the fight against COVID-19 by funding a number of hospitals. The organisation has promised to match every rupee given by an individual in order to reach its goal.

Findings:

- The ITC Limited firm spent Rs. 326.49 crores on CSR projects for one year.
- The Hindustan Unilever company spent more than 500 crores on its CSR operations in the last five years.
- In the past year, Nestlé India Limited has invested more than 38.31 crores in its CSR initiatives.
- In the past year, Britannia Nutrition Foundation has invested more than 2.25 crores in their CSR initiatives.
- Marico spent 19 crores of rupees on CSR initiatives in the past year.

Conclusion:

Through the Hindustan Unilever Foundation, the corporation carries out its CSR projects (HUF). The non-profit serves as a vehicle for Hindustan Unilever Limited's environmental and community development projects pertaining to water management. With an emphasis on empowering local community institutions to manage water resources and enhancing farm-based livelihoods through the adoption of wise water management techniques, HUF runs the "Water for

Public Good" initiative. Since 2010, 23 NGOs and over 4,300 villages in India have partnered with HUF to promote grassroots interventions in 53 districts. ITC partnered with Linde India to airfreight 24 cryogenic ISO containers, each weighing 20 tonnes, from Asian nations in order to deliver medical oxygen across India. This served the national priority of alleviating the bottleneck associated with transporting medical oxygen. The CSR project follows a severe medical oxygen shortage that is limiting the ability of the healthcare sector to treat coronavirus patients. Nestle is a firm believer in forming alliances with many stakeholders, such as local governments, academic institutions, civil society organisations, and so forth. During the fiscal year 2018–19, Nestle India Limited spent more on CSR initiatives than the required 2%. Although INR 38.07 crore was the required CSR spending as per Section 135 of the Companies Act, 2013, INR 38.31 crore was actually spent on CSR throughout the year. The provision of vital meals was at the top of the list of actions taken in reaction to the pandemic because food is the company's primary line of business. In 19 states, the Wadia Group distributed 1.35 billion meals (and meal equivalents) and 90 lakh packs of biscuits and bakery goods. The corporation contributed Rs. 12 crores to the effort to contain the epidemic during the COVID crisis. In some places, the corporation gave sanitizers worth Rs. 1 crore to front-line workers like government agencies, the police, hospitals, and medical staff. The business committed to working with GiveIndia to raise Rs. 2 crore. The money will be used to enhance the healthcare system in the fight against COVID-19 by funding a number of hospitals.

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